

made at Gobichettipalayam, Coimbatore.) When all TN1 seedlings were dead, the test seedlings were rated on a scale of 0 to 9 (0 = immune; 9 = very susceptible). Those whose grades were 3 or less are listed in the table.

Nira's rating was 0; further field tests in 1977 kharif and rabi confirmed the rating. Nira was not affected at all when caged with the insects.

Discontinuous variation in virulence of *Xanthomonas oryzae*

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We proposed a scheme, based on host-parasite interactions, to detect continuous and discontinuous variations in virulence of *Xanthomonas oryzae* on resistant rice. Figure 1 shows continuous variation in virulence among the isolates with no specificity in infection.

Results with the Philippine isolates and selected varieties with specific genes for resistance indicate that Pxo61 causes some lesions on varieties differing in specific resistance, yet it is more compatible with IR8, i.e. it produces larger lesions on varieties that have no functional genes for resistance in the Philippines. Likewise, Pxo79 causes more lesions on varieties with no functional genes and with the dominant gene *Xa4* for resistance. But Pxo71 is more specific to varieties with no functional gene and to varieties with the recessive gene *Xa5* for resistance. DV85, which has two genes for resistance, is resistant to all of those isolates; however, Pxo71 always seems to produce longer lesions than the two other isolates on that variety. (That may indicate the aggressiveness of the isolate. Analysis of variance suggested the interaction effect ($V \times I$) was highly significant.) The relative reaction among the selected differentials varied from one isolate to another. When the differential varieties were inoculated at different ages with these isolates, differential interactions between the isolates and the varieties were observed, showing specificity in infection between isolates and compatible varieties.

Rice varieties tolerant of root-knot nematode in rainfed areas

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Root-knot nematodes were observed on rainfed rice at the Ubon Rice Experiment Station, northeastern Thailand. The major soil texture of this predominantly

rainfed rice region is sandy loam. Average annual rainfall is 1,500 mm. Five genera of nematodes were identified; *Meloidogyne*, which was very active in the rice field, was the major genus.

Of 64 varieties screened for tolerance, 22 were found promising (from 4 to 25% root-knot infestation) (see table). Crop growth on those rices was normal.

Varieties will be inoculated with nematode egg mass in further trials, both in fields and in pots.

Promising varieties with tolerance for root-knot nematode. Ubon Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

Variety	Knot-formation (%)	Maturity (days)	Origin
RD6	4	144	Thailand
Burma Acc. 24161	5	not harvested	Burma
RD69 NF U-G-25	5	111	Thailand
Burma Acc. 24160	7	not harvested	Burma
Hawm Dong PMI 72-22	9	144	Thailand
147/54	10	111	Egypt
IR2071-636-5-5	15	111	IRRI
Hawm Dong PMI 72-40	15	144	Thailand
Amol/1-82	16		Egypt
KDML'65 G ₁ U-45	18	144	Thailand
RD2	18	125	Thailand
219/54	18	111	Egypt
IAC 1246	19	112	Brazil
RD7	20	111	Thailand
RD4	21	125	Thailand
158/54	21	111	Egypt
IR36	22	111	IRRI
IET4094	24	111	India
RD9	24	111	Thailand
Amol 1-78	25	111	Egypt
IR2061-465-1-5-5	25	112	IRRI
IR2071-625-1-252	25	112	IRRI

Effect of plant and leaf age on susceptibility to bacterial blight

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Rice plants are generally thought to be more susceptible to bacterial blight infection at the seedling than at the adult stage, and also to vary in resistance at different leaf ages. A variety's resistance or susceptibility to specific isolates appears independent of plant age but dependent on compatibility of host variety and isolate. Four varieties, IR8, IR20, IR1545, and DV85, were tested for resistance to the isolate Pxo82 at 9 to 37 days after seeding (DS). Pxo82

overcame the resistance of IR20 (*Xa4*) and IR8; the two varieties had long lesions that resulted in more infection at the seedling stage than IR1545 and DV85, which are resistant to Pxo82. Although lesions on those two varieties were longer at 9 than at 16 DS, their overall disease reactions at 9 DS were moderately resistant to resistant.

When individual leaves ranging from young to old were analyzed, significant interactions were noted among varieties but not among isolates. The interactions between varieties and isolates, however, were significant. When varietal resistance is evaluated with specific isolates, the leaf position at scoring may affect the reaction. On this basis, the varieties IR8,

IR1545, DV85, and RP291-20 were consistently resistant or susceptible to bacterial blight, while IR20 and Cempo

Selak varied in reaction. There was no longer any significant interaction with leaf positions within each group. Larger

differences in leaf position were detected among varieties of the latter than among those of the former group. *W*

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Transmission of rice ragged stunt disease by *Nilaparvata lugens* in Japan

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The transmission of rice ragged stunt disease by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* that had been reared on rice plants in Sapporo, Japan, for 4 years was studied. After 1-day acquisition feeding on diseased plants of the line IR3839-1, infected in the Philippines, 50 brown planthoppers (BPH) were tested for infectivity by daily serial transmission to 1,270 seedlings of the variety Mihonishiki for 40 consecutive days (except when insects died earlier). The experiment was carried out in a temperature-controlled greenhouse (25–28°C) at the University of Hokkaido, Japan.

Twenty-eight percent of the tested BPH were active transmitters. Both female and male adults and both brachypterous and macropterous forms were able to transmit the disease. The latent period ranged from 5 to 11 days after acquisition feeding, averaging 8.6 days. The infective insects transmitted the disease to 1 to 31 or more seedlings during their life spans. The retention period ranged from 9 to 41 days or more, after acquisition feeding (some insects did not die on the last day of the transmission test, 41 days after acquisition feeding). The disease-transmitting days were from 33 to 100% (av. 81%) of the period from the time the insects became infective until the end of the transmission test.

The BPH in Japan did not differ strikingly from the BPH in the Philippines in either percentage of active transmitters or latent period. But they

infected more rice seedlings during their life spans, had longer retention periods, and had higher percentages of disease-transmitting days than the Philippine BPH tested at IRRI.

Further studies will be conducted to determine if the differences are due to ecotype of the insect or conditions of the transmission test. *W*

Host range of rice ragged stunt virus

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Plants of several rice species were inoculated by brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* that were viruliferous for ragged stunt disease. Most of the plants did not become infected. Among *Oryza* species, however, *O. sativa*, *O. latifolia*, and *O. nivara* were all infected. The infected plants of *O. latifolia* (Fig. 1, 2) and *O. nivara*

(Fig. 3) showed symptoms of stunting, ragged leaves, vein swellings, and nodal branches. Those symptoms are similar to the ones on infected *O. sativa*.

Brown planthoppers recovered the virus from the diseased plants of *O. latifolia* and *O. nivara* and transmitted it successfully to rice plants.

Consequently, *O. sativa* is not the only host of ragged stunt. *W*

1. An *O. latifolia* plant infected with ragged stunt.
2. Ragged leaves of a diseased *O. latifolia* plant.
3. Healthy plants of *O. nivara* (left) and plants infected with ragged stunt (right).